

Skill Development Employability: In Rural Areas

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18639492

Abstract:

If we want to save the Konkan region, we must save its villages, and for that, people must continue to live there. Families are migrating from villages to cities in search of employment, and young people from the villages prefer to move to cities like Mumbai and Pune in search of jobs. As a result, villages are becoming deserted. This is adversely affecting village businesses, schools, and other small and large industries. Today, migrant laborers from other states are seen working in the mango industry, construction sector, and other fields. This is because our youth are migrating to cities in search of employment, and we have to rely on migrant laborers from other states for work in our own villages, thus providing them with employment. To stop all this, the youth of the villages should stay in their villages and create employment opportunities there. The modern era is an era of competition; competition is experienced in every aspect of life. This is disrupting the physical, mental, and economic balance of human life. Such a balance can only be found in rural areas. While economic and physical balance can be achieved in cities, a balance of mental, physical, and economic well-being can only be found in rural areas. Today, millions of tourists are visiting rural areas to experience mental peace. Taking advantage of this opportunity, people in rural areas should develop their inherent skills and strive to increase employment opportunities. This research paper studies the skills that can be developed to increase employment opportunities in rural areas. This includes studying businesses such as agro-tourism, handicraft industries, fisheries, agriculture-related businesses, pottery, mining, Konkani cuisine, event management, the hotel industry, and photography. In addition, while doing all this, the problems faced by people in rural areas and their solutions have also been studied

Introduction:

In the 21st century, securing good employment is becoming a significant challenge for the younger generation. The unemployment rate in 2025 was approximately 5.2%, and reducing this rate requires the development of employment opportunities. Although rural areas are larger in terms of geographical area, a large number of young people are migrating to urban areas for employment. To retain the population in rural areas, creating and expanding employment opportunities in villages is becoming essential.

Objective:

1. Studying the skills in rural areas.
2. Studying the employment potential generated from skills in rural areas.

3. To Study the problems in skill development in rural areas.
4. To Study the solutions to the problems in skill development in rural areas.

Research methodology:

The study is descriptive in nature. It is based on secondary data obtained from various articles, research paper, website from understanding the skill development employability in rural areas.

What is Rural Area?

A rural area is an agricultural region where there is a lower population density and a larger area connected to the natural environment. A village is a settlement within a rural area. In short, a rural area

is said to be a region where one experiences a greater proximity to nature. This area is usually located at a considerable distance from the city.

What is Skill Development Employability?

Here, skill refers to the ability to perform a task or activity effectively, accurately, and effortlessly. This is an ability that can be acquired through education, training, and practical experience, and continuously enhancing and progressing in this ability is what constitutes development. The ability to retain a job or business acquired based on these skills is called employability.

Considering the skills available in rural areas, there are many skills that can be utilized to create employment, and for this, people in rural areas do not need to undergo any training. On the contrary, individuals in rural areas can even provide training themselves and secure employment.

We will further study the employment opportunities that arise from skill development in these rural areas:

Agriculture:

In earlier times, agriculture was the primary occupation in rural areas. The person who cultivated the most land was considered the wealthiest. The villagers' wealth was not measured in money, but in the amount of food grains they had stored from their fields. However, over time, the scale of agriculture decreased. But if it is combined with modern technology, it can create immense employment opportunities. India's exports of agricultural and fisheries products, which were ₹2,49,264 crore in the financial year 2020, have increased to ₹4,33,819 crore by the financial year 2025, indicating a significant increase in the demand for agricultural products. Rural youth should take advantage of this and be encouraged to choose agriculture as a profession. Tourists coming from cities to villages are increasingly preferring to buy natural products from farms. Similarly, people from cities and even abroad are deliberately coming to villages to

experience the agricultural environment. This is how the concept of agritourism developed.

Agritourism:

India is an agrarian country. Since the concept of agritourism is related to agriculture, it has great potential for development here, creating an additional source of income for farmers. Agritourism involves tourists staying in agricultural areas and participating in farm work, experiencing the rural lifestyle. Activities such as riding bullock carts, performing actual farm tasks, strolling through fields and orchards, eating meals cooked on traditional stoves, dining amidst nature, and studying local culture are in demand among people from other countries. Since all these things are a part of the daily rural lifestyle, providing them will not be difficult, and this will also generate employment. In short, agritourism is a combination of agriculture and tourism.

Dairy Farming:

Dairy farming is a business that complements agriculture. As India is an agriculturally rich country, it has a large number of cows and buffaloes, making it the world's largest milk producer. The increasing population is driving up the demand for milk, leading to rapid growth in this industry. Small-scale farmers in rural areas also contribute significantly, accounting for approximately 62% of the country's total milk production. Through schemes like the Dairy Entrepreneurship Development Scheme, banks like NABARD are also providing subsidies of up to 33.33% on loans up to ₹7 lakh for the development of the dairy industry.

Poultry Farming:

Poultry farming is an integral part of the country's agricultural sector. It includes types such as backyard poultry farming, native chickens, egg-laying hens, and broiler chickens. It is an excellent way to provide the body with essential proteins, and today's youth are attracted to the products made from it. This is a highly profitable business that does not require a large capital investment; it is an

excellent way to earn a profit with minimal capital investment.

Kokani Mewa:

Tourists visiting rural areas are showing great interest in purchasing Konkani food products. These include items such as Kokum, Agal, rice, Kulith Flour, Groundnuts, Mangoes, Cashews, Jackfruit, Fish Masala, Kokum juice, Mango Pulp, Aambapoli, Fanaspoli, Aamras, Kairiche Panhe, Murabba, Farm-grown Pulses, Fried Jackfruit Segments, Betel nuts, Khaja (a sweet snack), and Coconut sweets, among many others. The people in these rural areas do not require any special training to make these products, as the methods have been passed down through generations. The sale of these products can generate significant employment, and they are also being sold online. Many examples can be cited, such as Yojak, Konkancha Raja, Oraskar, and Geeta Masale.

Handcraft:

Handicrafts include many arts such as sewing, embroidery, weaving, pottery, carpentry, making items from coconut shells, bamboo crafts, jute crafts, sculpting, and toy making. Additionally, in the Konkani region, where coconut trees are abundant, products such as brooms made from coconut fronds, and decorative items, earrings, necklaces made from conch shells and seashells are being produced. By increasing the production of these items and utilizing appropriate marketing strategies, employment opportunities can be created.

Hotel Industry:

The hotel industry is one of the largest businesses contributing to the country's economic progress in the 21st century. With the recent increase in tourism in rural areas, it has become an excellent source of employment generation. Tourists visiting rural areas enjoy experiencing the local food culture, including meals cooked on traditional stoves, Indian-style seating arrangements, meals served on banana leaves, and floors plastered with cow dung. Since all these things are naturally available, we can utilize them to create a great source of income. Considering the hotel industry's

contribution to the country's GDP, it was estimated at \$40 billion in 2022, and is projected to reach \$68 billion by 2027.

Marine Business:

India is a country surrounded by coastline on three sides; Maharashtra alone has a coastline of 720 kilometers. Millions of tourists visit these coastal rural areas to experience tranquility, and their main food is seafood. Since the people living on the coast have extensive experience in the fishing business, and it is an integral part of their daily lives, this presents an excellent opportunity for employment generation. There is a huge demand for seafood from the hotel industry. India accounts for about eight percent of the world's total fish production, making it the second largest producer globally. As a complementary business, industries such as boating, scuba diving, sea rides, and parasailing are currently generating employment on a large scale.

In this way, many small and large businesses are conducted through blacksmithing, goldsmithing, construction, digital services, event management, beekeeping, fish farming, spices, flour mills, and rice mills operated by self-help groups. The development and expansion of these businesses will only happen when the population in rural areas increases, and for this, the youth in rural areas should focus on creating employment opportunities locally instead of going to cities in search of jobs.

Problems of Skill Development and Employability creation in Rural Areas:

1. Incomplete knowledge
2. Lack of marketing skill
3. Language and communication skill problems
4. Lack of transportation service
5. Natural disaster
6. Incomplete knowledge of business related law
7. Low population business in rural areas
8. Low population
9. Lack of sufficient capital
10. Lack of willingness to take risks

Measures to Develop Skills-based employability:

The government is making many efforts to increase skill-based job creation in rural areas. This includes implementing various schemes to provide loans to rural people at affordable rates, as well as conducting various skill-based training programs. Through these initiatives, an attempt is being made to reduce unemployment in rural areas. Some of the government schemes are as follows:

1. Maharashtra State Agri and Rural Tourism Co-operative Federation Limited. -This includes objectives such as preserving local culture, skill development, increasing farmers' income, and promoting rural entrepreneurship.
2. Panchayat Samiti Kukatpalan Yojana -Under this scheme, subsidies are provided for constructing sheds, purchasing chickens, feed, and medicines.
3. Pradhan Mantri Matsya Sampada Yojana - Employment generation for local fishermen infrastructure and increase in exports.
4. Rashtriya Pashudhan Vikas Yojana - A subsidy of approximately 25% to 35% is provided for this business.
5. Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana - The Indian governments scheme provides loans ranging from 50,000 to 20,00,000 rupees to people of different age groups.
6. Aatmnirbhar Bharat Yojana-Up to 35% subsidy for industrial training and business.
7. Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana (DDU-GKY)-To Enhance the

employability of rural youth by developing their skills.

8. National Handicraft Development Programme (NHDP)- The main objective is to preserve and develop traditional handicrafts.
9. Pradhan Mantri Kisan Mandhan Yojana(PMKMY)-According to this farmers above sixty years of age will receive a monthly pension of three thousand rupees.
10. Rail Kaushal Vikas Yojana (RKVY)- Accordingly, the aim is to create employment opportunities by providing free training to young people aged 18 to 35.

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